

A BRIEF REVIEW OF EDUCATIONAL THERAPY & ITS CURRENT ROLE

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Introduction

Allied health professionals such as speech-language therapists (SLPs), physiotherapists (PTs), and occupational therapists (OTs) are commonly heard in Singapore as they offer their respective professional advice and specialized therapies to individuals, young and old, who need them, especially those with special needs. However, when the term educational therapist (ET) is mentioned, most parents and educators wonder what the job entails. In some way, they give a strange or puzzling look on their face. Many often mistake ETs to be specialist teachers that provide additional academic support to help weaker students.

In Singapore, OTs, PTs, and SLTs as well as diagnostic radiographers and radiation therapists are required by the Health Ministry to be registered with the Allied Health Professions Council (AHPC) under the Allied Health Professions Act 2011 (Attorney-General's Chambers Singapore, 2013) in order to practice. The AHPC governs and regulates the professional conduct and ethics of registered allied health professionals in accordance with the Allied Health Professions (AHP) Act 2011. In addition to the registration and issuing of practicing certificates, it also sets the standards for training, conduct, and practice and maintains the national register of allied health professionals in Singapore.

As for the ETs, it is not mandatory for them to be registered with the AHPC as they do not come under any statutory regulation here. Moreover, there is also a private registration body – The Registry of Educational Therapists Asia (RETA) – under the management of the Dyslexia Association of Singapore that represents the ETs based in Singapore and Asia, but not everyone is keen to register with the RETA. A small group of ETs here are registered members of the IACT.

The Historical Origin of Educational Therapy

The historical origin of Educational Therapy (abbreviated EdTx) began in the 1940s in Germany during World War II but it was not called educational therapy at that time. Known as *heilpädagogik* or therapeutic pedagogy (in the English translation), it is very much influenced by the work of two German pioneers August Aichorn (b.1878–d.1949) and Katrina DeHirsch (b.1903–d.1996). It was DeHirsch

(1977), who wrote about the 'Treatment Alliance' between the ET and the child, or interactions between the ET and his/her client, to distinguish the differences between educational therapy and psychotherapy. The field was somewhat eventually brought into the United States in the 1970s, and it is now widely known as Educational Therapy (EdTx) with the founding of the Association of Educational Therapists (AET) in 1978–79. Today, the AET is the US national professional association for educational therapists. The organization is dedicated to defining the professional practice of EdTx, setting standards for ethical practice, and promoting state-of-the-art service delivery through ongoing professional development and training programs. In addition, it provides information to the public about EdTx and facilitates access to EdTx services.

In the UK, EdTx is considered an appropriate mental health-cum-educational provision. The professional field began in the 1960s when Irene Caspari (b.1915–d.1976), who was born in Berlin, Germany, left for London, UK, to take the post of principal psychologist at the Tavistock Centre, London. Later, she became a leading trainer and exponent of a more psychoanalytic version of educational therapy (see Caspari, 1976, for detail). She established the Forum for the Advancement of Educational Therapy with her firm belief that a child might learn more effectively when an academic learning program went hand-in-hand with expressive work that delved into a child's deeper feelings if the ET was mindful of and able to engage the child's feelings as well as with his/her own relationship with the child as a learner. The term ET was later changed to an educational psychotherapist (EPT). Today, training to become an EPT is available to teachers and educational psychologists through the Caspari Foundation (see <http://www.caspari.org.uk> for detail), which also publishes its flagship journal – the Caspari Journal of Educational Psychotherapy. The educational psychotherapy has been recommended by the foundation to be included at later stages of the UK Code of Practice in a Statement of Special Educational Needs.

In summary of the development of EdTx, three main fields have come into play: Education, Psychology, and Therapy (see Figure 1). The Caspari model includes all three domains in its educational psychotherapy instead of the AET model of educational therapy, which sees it as

a clinical practice of utilizing specific methods, strategies, tools, and approaches to help support academic success in students.

Figure 1. Tripartite Model of Education–Psychology–Therapy

Under the purview of the World Health Organization (WHO), ET has been officially recognized and classified under the diagnostic code 93.82 since 1986 in the International Classification of Diseases, Clinical Modifications–ninth revision, volume 3 (ICD–9–CM, Version 3) (WHO, 1986).

Compounding the Definition of Educational Therapy

The term Educational Therapy (abbreviated EdTx) consists of two keywords: (1) Education; and (2) therapy.

First, the term Education (abbreviated Ed) refers to the process of facilitation of learning, i.e., in terms of acquisition of content knowledge, essential skills, values, morals, beliefs, habits as well as personal development. According to Peters & Hirst (1970), education involves the development of knowledge and understanding. It is seen as the liberation of the intellect from innocence to achieve rational autonomy.

Second, the term Therapy (abbreviated Tx) often refers to medical treatment. It is an attempted remediation of a health-related problem, usually following a diagnosis (medical or psycho-educational as well as projective and observational). There are many different types of therapy, and it is important to note that not all therapies are effective. There are also those therapies that can produce unwanted adverse effects. In the context of mental health or wellness, the term therapy may refer specifically to psychotherapy and/or other allied therapies.

As mentioned earlier, we have chosen to define EdTx – by compounding Ed and Tx – as a form of remedial treatment (see Figure 2) that “combines both educational (Ed) and therapeutic (Tx) approaches for evaluation, remediation, case management, and communication and/or advocacy on behalf of individuals of all ages with learning disabilities or learning problems” (Psychology Wiki, n.d., para. 4).

Figure 2. Educational Therapy as Remedial Treatment